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DDX helicase activation in childhood brain cancer.

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We measured total transcription in 124 brain tumors from children representing 7 separate pediatric CNS cancers and identified widespread DDX helicase activation in childhood brain cancer. These helicases included DDX42, DDX5, DDX3X, DDX19B, DDX20, and non-coding RNA that targets DDX19A, a divergent transcript for DDX19A (DDX19A-DT).